

ROOT CAUSE INVESTIGATION OF A NON-PHYSICAL TIME DOMAIN HARMONIC BALANCE SOLUTION

Sen Zhang

School of Power and Energy,
Northwestern Polytechnical University
Xi'an Shaanxi, China

Dingxi Wang

Shaanxi Key Laboratory of Internal
Aerodynamics in Aero-engines, Northwestern
Polytechnical University
Xi'an Shaanxi, China

ABSTRACT

The time domain harmonic balance method is an attractive reduced order method for analyzing unsteady flow within turbomachines. However, the method can admit non-physical solutions. Non-physical solutions were encountered from a three-blade-row compressor configuration in a time domain harmonic balance analysis. This paper aims to investigate the root cause of the non-physical solutions. The investigation involves several strategies, which include increasing the number of harmonics, increasing the number of time instants, including scattered modes, including the rotor-rotor interaction, and the use of a new method-the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method. Numerical analyses pertinent to each strategy are presented to reveal the root cause of the non-physical solution.

Keywords: the time domain harmonic balance method, non-physical solution, turbomachinery blade row interaction

1. INTRODUCTION

Frequency domain methods have been used as alternatives to time marching methods for resolving unsteady flow within turbomachines. Among all frequency domain methods, the time domain harmonic balance method [1] has gained popularity because it can be implemented on the basis of a steady flow solver with great ease. The method solves the unsteady flow governing equation at some selected time instants and the time discretization is achieved using a time spectral method. Due to the coupled solution at different time instants, the time domain harmonic balance approach can admit non-physical solutions [2]. It is also reported that non-physical solutions can be due to aliasing [3].

The time domain harmonic balance method was used to analyze unsteady flow within a three-blade-row configuration. Though a fully converged solution was obtained, a non-physical

solution was found in the middle blade row. Therefore, some investigations have been carried out on the three-blade-row configuration to find out the root cause of the non-physical solutions and remedies for them.

2. TEST CASE AND METHODS

2.1 Test case introduction

The three-blade-row configuration used in this investigation is taken from the front part of a replicant of the GE Energy Efficient Engine high pressure compressor, which can be obtained from the T-Axi tools [4]. Blade counts of the three rows (rotor, stator, and rotor) are 29, 51 and 38. The computational domain consists of one passage for each row. There are 57 grid points in the circumferential direction and 81 grid points in the spanwise direction for all rows. The number of grid points in the streamwise direction for the three rows is 129, 113 and 113, respectively. The total number of grid points is about 1.6 million. The meridional view and blade to blade view of the mesh are presented in Figure 1.

(a)

Figure 1 Meridional view (a) and blade to blade view at 50% span (b) of the mesh for the three-blade-row configuration.

2.2 Methodologies

The URANS equations with Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model [5] in a cylindrical coordinate system are solved by an in-house solver. The solver can employ the time domain harmonic balance method to analyze unsteady flow. The time and space mode decomposition and matching method is implemented in the solver for resolving blade row interactions [6]. Some studies about the harmonic balance in-house solver can be found in references [6,7,8].

To understand the root cause of and find remedy to the aforementioned non-physical solution, the following strategies are tried:

1. Increase the number of harmonics being retained in an analysis. In the configuration where the non-physical phenomenon occurs, the number of harmonics used for resolving the upstream wake and downstream potential disturbance are 6 and 3. It was speculated that the non-physical solutions were due to insufficient number of harmonics being retained in the analysis. Therefore, the number of harmonics for resolving the upstream wake and downstream potential field is increased to 10 and 5.

2. Include scattered modes in a harmonic balance analysis. For the three-blade-row configuration, the wake from the upstream and the potential disturbance from the downstream coexist in the middle blade row. The flow field of the middle blade row consists of two fundamental frequencies. Due to the nonlinearity of the unsteady flow, scattered modes will be generated. The frequencies and inter blade phase angles of scattered modes are subtraction (sub mode) or summation (sum mode) of the two fundamental frequencies and their higher harmonics.

3. Increase the number of time instants. In the harmonic balance approach, if the number of harmonics being retained in an analysis is N , then at least $2*N + 1$ time instants are needed. More than $2*N+1$ time instants have been used in the time domain harmonic balance method according to reference [9].

The number of time instants is also increased to see whether it can help stabilize a solution if there is a solution instability.

4. Resolve the rotor-rotor interaction unsteady flow. Due to the limitations of the time domain harmonic balance method, it cannot analyze a rotor-rotor interaction unsteady flow with a single passage domain. It is suspected that the non-physical solution may be due to the incapability of the time domain harmonic balance method in resolving rotor-rotor interaction flow components. The coupled time and passage spectral method [10] is used in this investigation to analyze the rotor-rotor interaction unsteady flow.

5. For the middle blade row, unsteady flow with two different fundamental frequencies should be resolved due to different blade passing frequencies (blade counts: 29/51/38). The Almost Periodic Fourier Transform (APFT) [11] algorithm is used to select the time instants in the time domain harmonic balance method. Since the non-physical solution appears in the middle blade row, the non-physical solution might be related to the way the unsteady flow with multiple fundamental frequencies is analyzed. A different reduced order method—the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method [12] is used to analyze the unsteady flow field with multiple fundamental frequencies.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The steady analysis is firstly performed. The uniform total pressure of 101325Pa and total temperature of 288.15K are specified at the inlet. The flow direction at the inlet is axial. An area averaged static pressure of 210.5kPa is specified at the outlet. A slip wall boundary condition with a wall function is used for an adiabatic wall. The convergence of the steady analysis can be seen in Figure 2. The convergence level can be considered acceptable although there are some oscillations in the residual. Figure 3 shows the relative Mach number contours at three representative spans. It can be observed that there is a very strong flow separation at 10% and 90% span of the middle blade row.

Figure 2 Convergence of the steady analysis with the back pressure of 210.5kPa (ρ represents the arithmetic average of the absolute density increment between consecutive pseudo iterations)

Figure 3 Relative Mach number contours at 10% (bottom), 50% (middle) and 90% span (top) with the back pressure of 210.5kPa.

The time domain harmonic balance analysis is initialized from the steady analysis. The time and space mode decomposition and matching method [6] is used for blade row coupling. Six harmonics are used to analyze an upstream wake and three harmonics are used for a downstream potential field (see Table 1). Figure 4 shows the convergence of the unsteady analysis. Several spikes in the residual can be observed. The first two spikes correspond to the reduction of the CFL number. The last spike is due to the shutdown of the machine where the computation was run. The solution is fully converged. Figure 5 shows the entropy contours at 50% span. The wake propagation at the middle blade row is incorrect. The solution is non-physical.

Table 1 Frequencies and inter blade phase angles (f_s represents the shaft frequency)

Rows	Frequency(Hz)	Inter blade phase angle($^\circ$)
Row1	$51 \cdot n \cdot f_s, n = 1, \dots, 3$	$\frac{360 \cdot 51 \cdot n}{29}, n = 1, \dots, 3$
Row 2	$29 \cdot n \cdot f_s, n = 1, \dots, 6$	$-\frac{360 \cdot 29 \cdot n}{51}, n = 1, \dots, 6$
	$38 \cdot n \cdot f_s, n = 1, \dots, 3$	$-\frac{360 \cdot 38 \cdot n}{51}, n = 1, \dots, 3$
Row 3	$51 \cdot n \cdot f_s, n = 1, \dots, 6$	$\frac{360 \cdot 51 \cdot n}{38}, n = 1, \dots, 6$

Figure 4 Convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with the back pressure of 210.5kPa

Figure 5 Entropy contours at 50% span when the back pressure is 210.5kPa

The non-physical solution occurred in the middle blade row, where there is strong flow separation. Therefore, it is very natural to put the blame of the non-physical solution on the flow separation. An operating point with a lower back pressure is chosen. The steady analysis with the back pressure of 150kPa is carried out. Figure 6 shows the convergence of the steady analysis. The solution converges without oscillation in the residual. The relative Mach number contours can be seen in Figure 7. The flow separation is smaller than that shown in Figure 3. The harmonic balance analysis is then performed at operating condition. The number of harmonics for resolving an upstream wake and a downstream potential field is still six and three. Figure 8 shows the convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with the back pressure of 150kPa. The discontinuity in the residual is due to the reduction of the CFL number. Figure 9 presents the entropy contours at the 50% span. Reduction of the back pressure does not eliminate the non-physical solution. Consequently, a series of strategies are adopted to eliminate the

non-physical solution of the middle blade row. The following analyses were performed with the back pressure of 150kPa.

Figure 6 Convergence of the steady analysis with the back pressure of 150kPa

Figure 7 Relative Mach number contours at 10% (bottom), 50% (middle) and 90% (top) span with the back pressure of 150kPa

Figure 8 Convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with the back pressure of 150kPa

Figure 9 Entropy contours at 50% span when the back pressure is 150kPa

3.1 Strategy 1: Increase the number of harmonics

The first strategy is quite straightforward. It is possible that the number of harmonics is not sufficient in this harmonic balance analysis. The number of harmonics being used for an upstream wake and a downstream potential disturbance was increased from 6 and 3 to 10 and 5. Figure 10 shows the convergence of the residual. The solution is fully converged. The entropy contours at 50% span look slightly better (see Figure 11). However, the non-physical solution still exists in the middle blade row. The number of harmonics is not increased further as retaining more harmonics will take much more time cost.

3.2 Strategy 2: Include scattered modes

There are two fundamental frequencies in the flow field of the middle blade row. Extra modes, whose frequencies are the subtraction or summation of the two fundamental frequencies and their higher harmonics, can be generated due to the nonlinearity of the flow governing equations. Such modes are called scattered modes in this investigation. Figure 12 shows the comparison of residual of the middle blade row when different scattered modes are included. The legend denotes the

configuration of harmonics for the middle blade row. The solution where only the harmonics for the upstream wake are specified has the best convergence (see 'nh_6' in Figure 12). The solution where no extra scattered modes are included (nh_6_3) has a similar convergence to that where two extra sub modes and extra sum modes (nh_6_3_-2_+2) are used. It comes to a relatively loose convergence level when there are only sub modes (nh_6_3_-2) or sum modes (nh_6_3_+2) being included. Figure 13 shows the comparison of the entropy contours. It is obvious that the flow field of the middle blade row is much better. The non-physical solution disappears when only the harmonics for an upstream wake are used (nh_6). The entropy contours still look good when there are only sub modes (nh_6_3_-2) or sum modes (nh_6_3_+2) being included although the solution has a loose convergence level.

It can be concluded from the analyses that the non-physical solution is due to the scattered modes being excluded from an analysis. The scattered modes are generated due to the nonlinearity of the governing equation and their influence cannot be ignored if their amplitudes are sufficiently large. However, including sub or sum scattered modes only significantly deteriorate the conditioning of the system, leading to a worse convergence.

Figure 10 Convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with an increased number of harmonics

Figure 11 Entropy contours at 50% span with an increased number of harmonics

Figure 12 Convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with different scattered modes(6: six harmonics for resolving an upstream wake, 3: three harmonics for resolving a downstream potential field non-uniformity,-2: two extra sub modes, +2:two extra sum modes)

Figure 13 Comparison of the entropy contours at 50% span with different scattered modes

3.3 Strategy 3: Increase the number of time instants

In the harmonic balance analysis, $2 \cdot N + 1$ time instants will be required if N harmonics are being retained. Ekici and Hall [9] used an oversampling method which requires $3 \cdot N + 1$ time instants to resolve unsteady flow with multiple fundamental frequencies. Increasing the number of time instants can help reduce the condition number of the inverse Fourier transform matrix, which can improve solution convergence. This investigation is based on the configuration where two extra sub modes (nh_6_3_-2) are considered in the middle blade row. There are in total 11 harmonics being retained in the time domain harmonic balance analysis, which requires at least 23 time instants. Figure 14 shows the comparison of the convergence with different time instants. Including 3 extra time instants (26 time instants) cannot improve the convergence and the flow field (see Figure 15). The solution cannot converge if 11 more time instants are included (34 time instants).

Figure 14 Convergence of the harmonic balance analysis with different time instants

Figure 15 Entropy contours at 50% span when the number of time instants is 26

3.4 Strategy 4: Resolve the rotor-rotor interaction unsteady flow

If we look at the entropy contours in the above sections, a clear discontinuity can be observed at the interface between the middle blade row and the third blade row. The wake from the first blade row cannot pass through the second interface because of the limitations of the method. To analyze unsteady flow using the time domain harmonic balance method with a single blade passage, the time averaged flow is assumed to be the same at different passages of the same row. The unsteady flow at different passages of the same row has the same amplitude and a constant phase difference. However, those assumptions are no longer valid in the rotor-rotor interaction analysis. It was speculated that the truncated wake at the second interface may lead to the non-physical solution of the middle blade row.

The coupled time and passage spectral method [10] is a very natural extension of the time domain harmonic balance method. The time averaged flow is approximated with spatial harmonics in the coupled time and passage spectral method, which can resolve flow components due to a rotor-rotor interaction. To analyze the wake from the first blade row in the third row, five extra modes are included in the row 3 domain (see Table 2). The solution has a tight convergence (see Figure 16). Figure 17 shows that the wake from the first blade row can pass through the second interface. But the non-physical solution at the middle blade row still cannot be eliminated.

Table 2 Configuration of extra frequencies and inter blade phase angles (f_s represents the shaft frequency)

Frequency(Hz)	Inter blade phase angle($^{\circ}$)
0	$\frac{360 \cdot 29}{38}$
$51 \cdot f_s$	$\frac{360 \cdot (51 + 29)}{38}$
$51 \cdot f_s$	$\frac{360 \cdot (51 - 29)}{38}$
$2 * 51 \cdot f_s$	$\frac{2 * 360 \cdot (51 - 29)}{38}$
$2 * 51 \cdot f_s$	$\frac{2 * 360 \cdot (51 + 29)}{38}$

Figure 16 Convergence of the coupled time and passage spectral analysis

Figure 17 Entropy contours of the coupled time and passage spectral analysis at 50% span

3.5 Strategy 5: The approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method

For the unsteady flow with a single fundamental frequency, the evenly spaced time instants over one period can ensure the minimum condition number of the inverse Fourier transform matrix. The flow field of the middle row consists of two fundamental frequencies. Inappropriate time instants will make the condition number of the inverse Fourier transform matrix bigger, which can lead to either bad convergence or solution instability. The Almost Periodic Fourier Transform (APFT) algorithm is used to select the time instants for a harmonic balance analysis. It was speculated whether excluding the direct interaction of flow components with different fundamental frequencies can help eliminate the non-physical solution. Consequently, the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method [12] is used in this analysis. The approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method puts different harmonic components into different groups based on their fundamental frequencies. Uniform time instants are used within each group. The solutions of each group are coupled through the time averaged solution.

The number of harmonics for the upstream wake and the downstream potential field is still 6 and 3 in the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method. The solution can have a tight convergence (see Figure 18). It is surprising to find that the non-physical solution at the middle blade row is eliminated (see Figure 19).

By analyzing the unsteady flow with different strategies, we can conclude that the cause of the non-physical solution is the nonlinear interaction of unsteady flow with two fundamental frequencies. If the harmonics for resolving the upstream wake only are retained in the middle blade row, the non-physical solution will not appear (see nh_6 in Figure 13). If the harmonics for the upstream wake and the downstream potential field non-uniformity are retained at the same time, extra scattered modes should be included to eliminate nonphysical solutions (see

Figure 13). The reason why the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method can eliminate the non-physical solution is that the direct nonlinear interaction between two different frequency groups is excluded in a solution and the interaction modes will be generated.

Figure 18 Convergence of the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic analysis

Figure 19 Entropy contours at 50% span when the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method is used

4. CONCLUSION

The non-physical flow field in the middle blade row of a three-blade-row configuration has been investigated. The root cause of the non-physical solution is due to the direct nonlinear interaction of unsteady flow components with different fundamental frequencies. Different strategies have been tried to eliminate the non-physical solution. Increasing the number of harmonics or time instants will have a limited impact on the solution. Resolving the rotor-rotor interaction unsteady flow does not eliminate the non-physical solution. To get rid of the non-physical solution, one can include extra scattered modes or use the approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method for this three-blade-row configuration.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China under the Grant No. of 51976172, the National Science and Technology Major Project (2017-II-0009-0023), and China's 111 project under the grant no. of B17037.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hall, K., Thomas, J., and Clark, W., 2002. "Computation of unsteady nonlinear flows in cascades using a harmonic balance technique". *AIAA Journal*, 40(5), pp. 879–886.
- [2] Liu, L., Thomas, J., Dowell, E., Attar, P., and Hall, K., 2006. "A comparison of classical and high dimensional harmonic balance approaches for a duffing oscillator". *Journal of Computational Physics*, 215(1), pp. 298–320.
- [3] Djeddi, R., and Ekici, K., 2016. "Resolution of gibbs phenomenon using a modified pseudo-spectral operator in harmonic balance cfd solvers". *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics*, 30(7-10), pp. 495–515.
- [4] Turner, M. G., Merchant, A., and Bruna, D., 2010. "A Turbomachinery Design Tool for Teaching Design Concepts for Axial-Flow Fans, Compressors, and Turbines". *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 133(3), July, p. 031017.
- [5] Spalart, P., and Allmaras, S., 1992. "A one-equation turbulence model for aerodynamic flows". In *Proceedings of 30th Aerospace Sciences Meeting and Exhibit*, Jan 06-09, Reno, NV, USA, Paper No. 92-0439.
- [6] Wang, D., and Huang, X., 2017. "A complete rotor-stator coupling method for frequency domain analysis of turbomachinery unsteady flow". *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 70, pp. 367–377
- [7] Wang, D., and Huang, X., 2017. "Solution stabilization and convergence acceleration for the harmonic balance equation system". *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 139(9).
- [8] Huang, X., Wu, H., and Wang, D., 2018. "Implicit solution of harmonic balance equation system using the LU-SGS method and one-step Jacobi/Gauss-Seidel iteration". *International Journal of Computational Fluid Dynamics*, 32(4-5), pp. 218–232.
- [9] Ekici, K., and Hall, K. C., 2007. "Nonlinear analysis of unsteady flows in multistage turbomachines using harmonic balance". *AIAA Journal*, 45(5), pp. 1047–1057.
- [10] Wang, D., Zhang, S., Huang, X., and Huang, H., 2022. "Coupled time and passage spectral method for an efficient resolution of turbomachinery far upstream wakes". *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 144(2), p. 021006.
- [11] Gudeney, T., Gomar, A., Gallard, F., Sicot, F., Dufour, G., and Puigt, G., 2012. "Non-uniform time sampling for multiple-frequency harmonic balance computations". *Journal of Computational Physics*, 236, pp. 317–345.
- [12] Wang, D., and Zhang, S., 2022. "An approximate time domain nonlinear harmonic method for analyzing unsteady flows with multiple fundamental modes". In *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2022: Turbine Technical Conference and Exposition*, June 13-17, Rotterdam, The Netherlands, Paper No. GT2022-81564.